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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FAST DISSOLVING TABLETS OF ARTEMETHER AND LUMEFANTRINE

R. Margret Chandira^{*}, B. S. Venkateshwarlu, A. Pasupathi, P. Palanisamy, K. Somu

Vinayaka Mission's College of Pharmacy, Vinayaka Mission's University, Salem (D.T), Tamil Nadu (State), India.

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ABSTRACT

Artemether and lumefantrine are antimalarial drugs used in the management of malaria. The objective of the proposed research work is to prepare and evaluate the fast dissolving tablets (FDTs) of artemether and lumefantrine, which avoid the first-pass metabolism, improved the dissolution rate and enhance the bioavailability. Fast dissolving tablets (FDTs) were prepared by direct compression method by using combination of superdisintegrant like, Crosspovidone and sodium starch glycolate(5%,10%,&15%) and evaluated for physico-chemical evaluation parameter such as hardness, friability, weight variation, drug content uniformity, water absorption ratio, wetting time, *in-vitro* andisintegration time, *in-vitro* dissolution studies. The control tablet (without superdisintegrant) was formulated and evaluated. The 12 formulations, F1to F6 were formulated and among these formulations, F3 (crosspovidine) was optimized. The hardness, friability, weight variation and drug content were found to be within pharmacopeias limits. The water absorption ratio, wetting time, *in-vitro* disintegration time of optimized formulation, F3 was found to be 62.87%, 12secs and 15secs respectively. The formulation, F3 was considered to best formulation, which released up to 99.49% (artemether) & 99.15% (lumefantrine)in 25 minutes. The comparison of dissolution rate profile of formulation and controlled formulation of artemether and lumefantrine tablet with best formulation, F3 was conducted. The result showed that the formulation, F3showed complete drug release within 25 minutes and controlled formulation showed 26.50% (artemether) &24.50%(lumefantrine) drug release in 25 minutes. The stability study was also conducted the best formulation, F3 and it indicates that there was no significant change in any parameters. Hence the formulation F3 was considered to be highly stable.

Corresponding author

R. Margret Chandira

M.Pharm, Ph.D,

Department of Pharmaceutics,

Vinayaka Mission's College of Pharmacy,

Yercaud Main Road,

Kondappanaickenpatty, Salem (D.T),

Tamil Nadu (State)-636 008.

mchandira172@gmail.com

94430-09862

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of fast dissolving drug delivery system emerged from the desire to provide patient with more conventional means of taking their medication. Many patients face difficulty to swallow tablets and hard gelatin capsules. Hence, they do not comply with prescription, which results in high incidence of non-compliance and ineffective therapy.

In the present study an attempt has been made to formulate fast dissolving tablets of arthemether and lumefantrine using superdisintegrants like sodium starch glycolate and croscopolvidone, In this investigation the effect of different superdisintegrants on various parameters of tablets has been studied and functionality differences have been evaluated. The aim of this study was to enhance the efficacy of drug molecule, achieve better compliance, enhance onset of action, and provide stable dosage form.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Arthemether and lumefantrine was Gifted by Hetro drugs., Hyderabad, B-cyclodextrin Croscopolvidone, Sodium Starch glycolate, Anhydrous sodium bicarbonate & Light magnesium carbonate was gifted by Nikitha chemicals, India, Mannitol, Aspartame, Aerosil, Talc, Magnesium stearate was gifted by Vasundhara rasayans ltd, India.

UV Spectrophotometric Analysis:

Preparation of standard stock solution

50mg of arthemether transferred into 50ml volumetric flask. It was dissolved in methanol and volume was made up to the mark with phosphate buffer 6.8. This gives stock solution of concentration (100mg/ml), from this 5ml was with drawn and diluted to 50ml to get a concentration of (10mg/ml)⁴.

Standard curve preparation of Artemether

From this standard solution stock solution, aliquots 1,2,3,4,5,10ml were with drawn and made up to 10ml phosphate buffer 6.8 to give a concentration of 1,2,3,4,5,10mg/ml. Absorbance of these solution was measured 254nm⁵.

Preparation of standard stock solution

50mg of lumefantrine transferred into 50ml volumetric flask. It was dissolved in methanol and volume was made up to the mark with phosphate buffer 4.5. This gives stock solution of concentration (100mg/ml), from this 5ml was with drawn and diluted to 50ml to get a concentration of (10mg/ml).

Standard curve preparation of lumefantrine

From this standard solution stock solution, aliquots 1,2,3,4,5,10ml were with drawn and made up to 10ml phosphate buffer 4.5 to give a concentration of 1,2,3,4,5,10mg/ml. Absorbance of these solution was measured 315nm.

The results were mentioned in the table. No: 2 - 3

Infra-red Spectrophotometric analysis

The pellets were made with mixing 1gm of drug and 100gm of dried potassium bromide powder. Mixer was then compressed under 10-ton pressure in a hydraulic press to form a transparent pellet. The thin pallet was put on pellet disc to get IR Spectra⁶.

The results were mentioned in the Figure. No: 1 - 5

Preformulation Studies

Preformulation study relates to pharmaceutical and analytical investigation carried out proceeding and supporting formulation development efforts of the dosage form of the drug substance. Preformulation yields basic knowledge necessary to develop suitable formulation for the toxicological use. It gives information needed to define the nature of the drug substance and provide frame work for the drug combination with pharmaceutical excipients in the dosage form⁷.

Bulk Density (Db), Tapped Density (Dt), Angle of Repose (θ), Carr's index (or) % compressibility and Hausner ratio

The results were mentioned in the table. No: 4

Manufacturing method**Table. No.1 Formulation of fast dissolving tablet.**

Sr.no	Ingredients	F0	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1	B-cyclodextrins	240	240	240	240	240	240	240
2	Sodiumbicarbonate	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
3	magnesium carbonate	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
4	Artemether	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
5	Mannitol	100	95	90	85	95	90	85
6	Aspartame	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
7	Aerosil	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
8	Citric acid	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
9	crosspovidine	-	5	10	15	-	-	-
10	Sodium starch glycolate	-	-	-	-	5	10	15
11	Talc	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
12	Magnesium stearate	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
	Total weight	410	410	410	410	410	410	410

Evaluation Fast Dissolving Tablets⁸⁻¹⁰**Weight variation test:**

20 tablets were selected randomly from the lot and weighted individually to check for weight variation. Weight variation specification as per I.P. is shown in

The results were mentioned in the table. No:5

Hardness test:

Hardness or tablet crushing strength (fc), the force required to break a tablet in a diametric compression was measured using Monsanto tablet hardness tester. It is expressed in kg/cm².

The results were mentioned in the table. No: 5

Thickness

The thickness of tablets was determined using a Digimatic vernier caliper (Mitutoya, Japan). Three tablets from each batch were used, and average values were calculated.

The results were mentioned in the table. No: 5

Friability (F):

Friability of the tablet determined using Roche friabilator. This device subjects the tablet to the combined effect of abrasion and shock in a plastic chamber revolving at 25 rpm and dropping a tablet at height of 6 inches in each revolution. Pre-weighted sample of tablets was placed in the friabilator and were subjected to the 100 revolutions. Tablets were dusted using a soft muslin cloth and reweighed. The friability (F) is given by the formula.

$$F = \frac{W_{\text{initial}} - W_{\text{final}}}{W_{\text{initial}}} \times 100$$

Acceptance criteria for % friability, % weight loss should be less than 1%

The results were mentioned in the table. No: 5

Finished product parameter**Disintegration time testing**

It was determined using USP tablet disintegration test apparatus, using 900ml of distilled water without disk at room temperature. Test was performed on 6 tablets. Limit set for the disintegration time: not more than 30 seconds.

The results were mentioned in the table. No: 6

In vitro dispersion time:

For determination of in vitro dispersion time, one tablet was placed in a beaker containing 10ml of PH 6.8 phosphate buffer at 37±0.5°C and the time required for complete dispersion was determined. The test was repeated on three other tablets of same batch, the average gives in vitro dispersion time

Wetting time of tablet

Wicking time test gives the idea on porosity, compressibility as well as absorption capacity of the tablets. Since the dissolution process of a tablet depends upon the wetting followed by disintegration of the tablet, the measurement of wetting times may be used as another confirmative test for the evaluation of tablets.

Procedure:

For determination of wetting time, piece of tissue paper folded twice was placed in a small Petri dish (internal diameter of 5 cm) containing 6ml of water. A tablet was carefully placed on the surface of tissue paper. The time required for water to reach the upper surface of the tablets was noted as the wetting time. The test was repeated on the three other tablets of the same batch in same Petri dish and average of the three readings gives then means wetting time of the tablets. The results were mentioned in the table. No: 7

Water absorption Ratio

A piece of tissue paper folded twice was placed in a small Petri dish containing 6 ml of water. A tablet was put on the paper & the time required for complete wetting was measured . The wetted tablet was then weighed. Water absorption ratio, R, was determined using following equation,

$$R=100(Wb-Wa) /Wa$$

where, Wa is weight of tablet before water absorption
Wb is weight of tablet after water absorption.

ASSAY (ARTEMETHER):

Twenty tablets from each batch were weighed accurately and powdered powder equivalent to 100mg artemether was shaken with 100ml of 6.8 phosphate buffer in 100ml amber colored volumetric flask and from this 10ml pipette out and dilute upto 100ml. from standard solution again 10ml pipette out and diluted upto 100ml in 100ml amber colored volumetric flask. resulting solution was filtered and assayed at 254nm and content of artemether was calculated. The results were mentioned in the table. No: 5

ASSAY (LUMEFANTRINE):

Twenty tablets from each batch were weighed accurately and powdered powder equivalent to 100mg lumefantrine was shaken with 100ml of 4.5 phosphate buffer in 100ml amber colored volumetric flask and from this 10ml pipette out and dilute upto 100ml. from standard solution again 10ml pipette out and diluted upto 100ml in 100ml amber colored volumetric flask. resulting solution was filtered and assayed at 310nm and content of lumefantrine was calculated. The results were mentioned in the table. No: 5

In vitro drug release study (artemether):

The release rate of drug from FDT was determined using USP Dissolution testing apparatus II (paddle method). The dissolution medium was 6.8ph phosphate buffer, the volume being 900ml. the temperature was maintained at $37\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. the rotation speed was 50rpm. A sample (5ml) of the solution was withdrawn from the dissolution apparatus at 5,10,15,20 and 25 minutes. And the samples were replaced with fresh dissolution medium. The samples were filtered through a membrane filter and absorbance of these solutions was measured at 254nm using a UV/V is double-beam spectrophotometer of Cumulative percentage drug release was calculated using linear equation obtained from a standard curve. The results were mentioned in the Table. No: 5, 8 & 9

In vitro drug release study(lumefantrine):

The release rate of drug from FDT was determined using (USP XXIII)⁶⁷ Dissolution testing apparatus II (paddle method). The dissolution medium was 4.5PH phosphate buffer, the volume being 900ml. the temperature was maintained at $37\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. the rotation speed was 50rpm. A sample (5ml) of the solution was withdrawn from the dissolution apparatus at 5,10,15,20and 25 minutes. And the samples were replaced with fresh dissolution medium. The samples were filtered through a membrane filter and absorbance of these solutions was measured at 310nm using a UV/V is double-beam spectrophotometer of Cumulative percentage drug release was calculated using linear equation obtained from a standard curve. The results were mentioned in the Table. No: 5, 8 & 9

Stability studies**Introductions**

Stability of a drug can be define as the time from the date of manufacture and the packaging of the formulation, until its chemical or biological activity is not less then a predetermined level of labeled potency and its physical characteristics have not changed appreciably or deleteriously. In any design and evaluation of dosage forms for drugs, the stability of the active component must be a major criterion in determining their acceptance or rejection.

Stability Studies¹⁰⁻¹¹

Stability of a drug can be define as the time from the date of manufacture and the packaging of the formulation, until its chemical or biological activity is not less then a predetermined level of labeled potency and its physical characteristics have not changed appreciably or deleteriously. In any design and evaluation of dosage forms for drugs, the stability of the active component must be a major criterion in determining their acceptance or rejection.

In the present work stability study was carried out for the optimized formulation at $40^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/75\%\text{RH}\pm 5\%\text{RH}$ for three month.

The results were mentioned in the Table. No: 10-12 .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

Table. No: 2 Standard curve of lumefantrine.

Sr.No.	Conc. (mcg/ml)	UV absorbance
1	0	0
2	2	0.125
3	4	0.248
4	6	0.362
5	8	0.486
6	10	0.611
7	12	0.729
8	14	0.850
9	16	0.962
10	18	1.089

Beer-Lambert's law was obeyed over the range and data was found to fit the equation $R^2=0.9994$, Slope=0.058

Conclusion

The standard curve prepared shown very linearity hence it was used for further analysis.

Table. No: 3 Standard curve of Artemethar.

Sr no	Conc (mcg/ml)	ABS (nm)
1	2	0.115
2	4	0.229
3	6	0.338
4	8	0.454
5	10	0.568
6	12	0.675
7	14	0.788
8	16	0.899
9	18	0.998

Beer-Lambert's law was obeyed over the range and data was found to fit the equation $R^2=0.9992$, Slope=0.055

Conclusion

The standard curve prepared shown very linearity hence it was used for further analysis

Infra-Red Spectrophotometric analysis

Using IR spectrometer carried out the analytical studies of the drug and FDT product. The characteristic peaks are listed in the table. IR spectroscopic studies indicated that the drug is compatible with all the excipients.

Fig no: 1 IR Spectra of drug (Artemether) :

Fig no: 2 IR Spectra of drug (Lumefantrine) :

Fig no:3 IR Spectra of drug (Artemether+Lumefantrine):

Fig no: 4 IR Spectra of drug (Artemether+Lumefantrine+Sod.Starch Glycolate) :

Fig No 5:Ir Spectra of Drug(Artemether+Lumefantrine+Crosspovidone):

Table. No: 4 Evaluation of Blend.

Batch code	Bulk Density (gm/ml)	Tapped Density (gm/ml)	Angle of Repose	Carr's index	Hausner Ratio
F0	0.62	0.68	29 ⁰ 13	19.43	1.096
F1	0.55	0.66	28 ⁰ 38	16.69	1.131
F2	0.60	0.66	30 ⁰ 38	16.66	1.141
F3	0.60	0.74	29 ⁰ 79	19.43	1.233
F4	0.58	0.66	30 ⁰ 38	16.66	1.137
F5	0.56	0.64	28 ⁰ 79	15.55	1.107
F6	0.56	0.65	27 ⁰ 23	13.84	1.160

CONCLUSION

As per flow ability scale, the drug has good characteristics to flow. The excipients did not make any effect on the flow of blend. Thus it was decided to use direct compression method.

Evaluation of Physical Parameters of the FDT Formulations

Table. No:5-Evaluation Parameters of Batch F0 to F6.

Parameters	F0	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Weight variation (mg)	408.48	406	404.80	405.6	407	406.40	408
Thickness(mm)	3.50±0.055	3.5±0.017	3.53±0.025	3.52 ±0.04	3.52 ±0.04	3.50 ±0.251	3.54 ±0.05
Hardness(kg/cm ²)	3.50±0.04	3.50±0.08	3.50 ±0.03	3.83 ±0.09	3.50 ±0.04	4.00 ±0.05	3.66 ±0.01
Friability(% w/w)	0.40%	0.41%	0.41%	0.51%	0.45%	0.43%	0.39%
Disintegration time (sec)	200 sec	19 sec	16 sec	15 sec	28sec	24sec	19sec
Wetting time(sec)	176±1.527	23	15	12	26	23	19
Assay(%) (artemether)	97.85	98.52	99.67	100.10	99.75	99.63	100
Assay(%) (lumefantrine)	98.65	98.65	99.45	100.50	99.65	99.75	100.10
Water Absorption Ratio(%)	56.45	57.51	59.97	62.87	60.96	61.32	66.45
Invitro dispersion Time(sec)	155±1	18±1	13±0.76	10 ±0.63	19±0.5	15±1	11±0.5

All values mean± S.D

Comparative Study of Disintegration Time of Formulations F1 To F6

Table. No: 6 Disintegration time of formulation F1 to F6.

Superdisintegrant	Formulation	Disintegration time (Sec)
Crosspovidine	F1	19
	F2	16
	F3	15
Sodium starch glycolate	F4	28
	F5	24
	F6	19

Wetting Time of Formulations:-

Table No: 7 Wetting Time of Formulation.

Superdisintegrant	Formulation	Wetting time (sec)
Crosspovidine	F1	23
	F2	15
	F3	12
Sodium starch glycolate	F4	26
	F5	23
	F6	19

Dissolution Profile of FDT Formulations

Table. No: 8:- Percentage Cumulative drug release profile of Batch F0 to F6 Artemether.

Time (min)	F0	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	5.07	28.47	32.40	33.07	23.07	25.03	30.60
10	9.46	44.97	47.45	50.40	40.40	43.36	45.65
15	15.36	57.27	64.63	70.52	53.83	56.94	63.16
20	21.43	72.81	79.83	86.40	68.89	72.49	78.05
25	26.01	85.25	92.45	99.49	82.14	88.20	91.63

Table. No:9 Percentage Cumulative drug release profile of Batch F0 to F6 Lumefantrine.

Time (min)	F0	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	4.50	27.93	29.32	30.35	26.53	28.08	29.48
10	9.00	41.74	43.13	45.93	40.03	42.51	44.37
15	14.74	55.55	58.80	60.36	52.91	57.25	58.65
20	19.55	72.15	77.27	79.91	71.22	73.08	78.98
25	24.12	84.10	91.70	99.15	82.39	89.22	92.79

STUDY OF OPTIMIZED FORMULATION F-3 USING (CROSSPOVIDINE IN 15%)

It is very essential that any product developed in the formulation department should be stable. The regulatory agencies in different countries try to ensure that the stability studies are carried out on the product. The formulation is subjected to accelerated stability conditions ($40^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\%$). The effects of temperature and time on the physical and chemical characteristics of the tablet were evaluated for assessing the stability of the formulated tablets. The results indicate that there wasn't any significant change in hardness & % drug content. There is a significant weight gain and increased wetting time. Disintegration and in vitro drug release was found to be increased a little more at 40°C temperature. No significant change was observed in drug content.

Accelerated stability studies as per ICH guidelines:

The optimized formulation (F3) was wrapped in aluminum foils and kept in Petri-dish at ($40^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\%$) in humidity chamber. The stability studies were conducted after 15 and 30 days.

Table. No:10 Physical Characteristics of Artemether and Lumefantrine Fast dissolving tablet of optimized Batch F3 at Temperature ($40^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\%$).

Physical parameters	0day	30days	90days
Percentage drug content (%) (arte&lume)	99.49 & 99.15	99.49 & 99.15	99.19 & 98.94
Hardness (kg/cm^2)	3.83	3.83	3.79
Disintegration time(sec)	15sec	15sec	16sec
Wetting time(sec)	12sec	12sec	13sec

Table. No:11 %Drug release at ($40^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\%$) Of optimized Batch F3.

Artemether

Time (min)	%Drug release in 0day	%Drug release in 30days	%Drug release in 90days
0	0	0	0
5	33.07	33.07	32.62
10	50.40	50.40	49.96
15	70.52	70.52	70.39
20	86.40	86.40	86.24
25	99.49	99.49	99.15

Table. No: 12 %Drug release at ($40^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/75\% \text{RH} \pm 5\%$) Of optimized Batch F3.

Lumefantrine

Time (min)	%Drug release in 0day	%Drug release in 15days	%Drug release in 30days
0	0	0	0
5	30.25	30.25	30.13
10	45.93	45.93	45.76
15	60.36	60.36	60.19
20	79.91	79.91	77.34
25	99.15	99.15	98.94

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Artemether and lumefantrine is a artemisinin combination therapy (ACT) is widely used in acute uncomplicated resistant falciparum malaria should be treated only combining one of the artemisinin compound with another effective erythrocytic schizonticide. The concept of formulating orally disintegrating tablets of artemether&lumefantrine offer a suitable and practical approach in serving desired objective of faster disintegration and dissolution characteristic with increase bioavailability. Therefore, in order to get better patient compliance in the treatment, it is necessary to design a new drug delivery system of the drug artemether&lumefantrine i.e. orally disintegrating tablets. The focus of the present investigation is to minimize disintegration time and improved drug release with faster onset of action.

Conventional artemether&lumefantrine tablets available in market are not suitable where quick onset of action is requires. To overcome these problems, there is a need to develop a rapidly disintegrating dosage form, particularly one that would rapidly disintegrate in saliva and could be administered without water anywhere anytime. No such fast dissolving tablet of artemether&lumefantrine is available.

The drug excipients compatibility studies were carried out to FT-IR analysis, it showed that there was on interaction between the drug and excipients chosen of formulation.

The results of all formulations for weight variation, Friability, hardness and Assay were found to be within the standard pharmacopoeial limit. Overall, the formulation F3 containing 15% w/w of croscopovidine was found to be promising and has show an in vitro dispersion time 10 sec and disintegration time 15sec, wetting time of 12 sec and water absorption ratio of 62.83% when compared to control formulation (F0) which shows 155sec, 200 sec, 176 s and 56.45% values respectively for the above parameter. The experimental data also shows that the results obtained from croscopovidine are comparable and even slightly better then those of ssg. And the Formulation F3 shows faster drug release when compared to a commercial conventional tablet of croscopovidine.

The stability studies were performed per I.C.H guidelines. Formulation F3 was selected as per its content uniformity, in-vitro disintegration time, wetting time, hardness test, and in-vitro drug release study. The formulation showed no significant variations in all parameters and was stable for a period of 90 days.

The tablets prepared were found to be good, without chipping and sicking with optimum hardness and thickness. The tablets prepared by using croscopovidine in 15% ratio were found to be disintegrate faster and there is rapid drug relse within short time and found to be stable. The rate of drug relse is increased and disintegration time is decreased to a considerable effect by increasing the concentration of superdisintegrants. Thus it can be concluded that as the concentration of superdisintegrant is increased the rate of drug release and disintegration time is enhanced. This study demonstrated that disintegration of artemether and lumefantrine can be enhanced to a great extent by direct compression technique with addition of combination of superdisintegrants.

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